

Overcoming Parcel Delineation Constraints in Georgia Using Multi-Source Satellite Imagery

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Abstract: Accurate parcel delineation is a fundamental prerequisite for effective land administration, agricultural monitoring, and evidence-based policy making. In Georgia, the parcel delineation encounters multiple challenges. First, high-resolution aerial imagery is not available on a regular, annual basis, limiting consistent updating of parcel boundaries. Second, agricultural land in Georgia is highly fragmented, with small, irregularly shaped parcels that complicate boundary identification with medium-resolution data. Although the systematic registration of agricultural parcels was completed in 2025, major shortcomings persist concerning the current cultivation status of registered parcels and the spatial scope of abandoned agricultural land. This study explores the potential of multi-source satellite imagery to overcome these restrictions using automated parcel delineation. The research integrates Sentinel-2 multispectral time series, high-resolution PlanetScope imagery, aerial photographs, and official cadastral data to train and validate parcel delineation models within the Google Earth Engine (GEE) environment. Multi-temporal spectral metrics, texture features, and phenological information are used to enhance the separability of homogeneous agricultural units and improve boundary detection accuracy. The method is tested in two municipalities: Dedoplistskaro, dominated by large-scale annual crops, and Gori, characterized by orchards with complex canopy structures and fragmented parcel patterns. The findings show that combining medium-resolution temporal information from Sentinel-2 with the spatial detail of PlanetScope significantly improves automated parcel delineation compared to single-sensor approaches. The proposed workflow provides a framework for identifying cultivated and potentially abandoned parcels, offering a useful basis for agricultural monitoring and land management in data-limited environments such as Georgia.

Keywords: agriculture parcel; delineation; PlanetScope; Georgia.

1 Introduction

Agricultural parcel maps play a central role in land administration systems, supporting farm monitoring, subsidy allocation, and sustainable land management practices (Longley et al. 2015, FAO 2012). They are also increasingly important for implementing precision agriculture technologies and guiding rural development policies (Zhang et al. 2012). Despite their importance, producing accurate parcel maps remains a difficult task in

many countries with fragmented land ownership structures, including Georgia. After gaining independence (1991), the process of land privatization began in Georgia, although it was mainly based on sporadic registration. As a result, a highly fragmented land use was formed, which is complicated by the large number of unregistered and unofficially used parcels.

One of the main challenges comes from the physical characteristics of agricultural land. Parcels are often small, irregular, and intermixed with different land-use types. This makes it difficult to delineate boundaries using medium-resolution imagery alone (Persello et al. 2019). At the same time, access to high-resolution data is limited and not always available on a regular basis, which further complicates the process.

Recent developments in cloud computing platforms such as Google Earth Engine (GEE) have made it possible to process large volumes of satellite data more efficiently (Gorelick et al. 2017). This has opened new opportunities for combining multiple Earth observation datasets. For example, Sentinel-2 imagery provides high temporal resolution and spectral richness, which are useful for capturing crop growth patterns and seasonal dynamics (Drusch et al. 2012). In contrast, very high-resolution imagery such as PlanetScope offers the spatial detail needed to detect field boundaries more precisely (Houborg and McCabe 2016).

Previous studies have shown that combining these complementary datasets can significantly improve classification results and object-based image analysis (Immitzer et al. 2016, Belgiu and Csillik 2018). At the same time, automated parcel delineation methods have evolved considerably, moving from traditional segmentation techniques toward machine learning and deep learning approaches (Zhu et al. 2017). While these methods have shown strong performance, their effectiveness is often limited in environments where high-quality data are scarce or inconsistent.

Another important aspect that has received increasing attention is the functional status of agricultural parcels. Beyond identifying boundaries, there is a need to distinguish between actively cultivated and abandoned land. Multi-temporal vegetation indices, particularly NDVI, have proven useful in capturing such dynamics and identifying fallow areas (Estel et al. 2016, Griffiths et al. 2013).

Accordingly, the goal of this study is to automatically delineate agricultural parcels using open access data.

2 Materials and methods

The study was conducted in two municipalities of Georgia—Gori and Dedoplistskaro Municipalities (Figure 1). Gori Municipality, located in Shida Kartli, is characterized by fragmented arable land parcels. Of the total area of the municipality (130041 ha), 23.3 ha are occupied by annual crops, and 13789 ha by perennial crops. For the present study, a village was selected in Gori Municipality, which is characterized by fragmented land parcels and perennial crops.

Figure 1. Study area: 1-in Gori Municipality, 2-in Dedoplistskaro Municipality.

In contrast, In Dedoplistskaro Municipality, located in Kakheti, annual crops (mainly wheat and barley) are the leading crops. Out of the total area of the municipality (239611 ha), 55183 ha are occupied by annual crops. In the present Dedoplistskaro Municipality, an area was selected where 90% of the plots are occupied by annual crops.

Multi-source satellite imagery was used to capture both spatial detail and temporal dynamics of agricultural land. For Gori Municipality, PlanetScope imagery was acquired for eight months (March–October 2025), providing near-daily, high-resolution (approximately 3 m) observations. This period coincides with the growing season of perennial crops in the study area. Corresponding Sentinel-2 imagery (10 m spatial resolution) was obtained for the same period to ensure temporal consistency and to support phenological analysis.

For Dedoplistskaro Municipality, PlanetScope imagery was collected for four key months (April–July 2025), aligned with the main growing season of annual crops. Sentinel-2 data for the same time frame were also incorporated. All Sentinel-2 images were atmospherically corrected (Level-2A) and filtered for cloud contamination using quality masks. In addition to satellite imagery, ancillary cadastral data were used for validation purposes, providing reference parcel boundaries where available. These datasets supported the assessment of delineation accuracy and helped guide parameter tuning during model development. All satellite data preprocessing and analysis were conducted in GEE, which enabled efficient handling of multi-temporal datasets and large-scale computations (Figure 2). The accuracy of parcel delineation was evaluated by comparing generated parcel boundaries with available cadastral data and visual interpretation of high-resolution imagery.

Figure 2. Methodological workflow.

Metrics such as boundary overlap, omission and commission errors, and overall delineation accuracy were assessed. Particular attention was given to differences in performance between the fragmented landscape of Gori and the more homogeneous agricultural fields of Dedoplistskaro, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the methodology under diverse conditions.

3 Results

The aim of the study was to assess the feasibility of automatically delineating agricultural parcels in selected villages in the Gori and Dedoplistskaro municipalities. Figure 3 shows that the first area (274.5 ha) includes settlements, roads, agricultural and non-agricultural parcels, while the second area (2703.4 ha) is almost entirely agricultural parcels.

Figure 4 clearly shows the difference between the parcels delineated using Sentinel 2 alone and Sentinel 2+Plantscope. Using PlanetScope allowed us to delineate the parcels with greater accuracy. In this case, the edges of the parcels improved. Although the number of small and unnecessary parcels increased in this case, during the subsequent generalization process, these unnecessary parcels merged into larger parcels, while many important parcels "disappeared" in the Sentinel 2-based process. In conditions of such fragmentation, this further reduces the accuracy of the process.

However, challenges remained in areas with dense tree cover and overlapping canopies, where boundary detection was less distinct. In such cases, the inclusion of high-resolution PlanetScope imagery enhanced edge detection and reduced boundary smoothing effects commonly observed in medium-resolution datasets. Quantitatively, the delineation accuracy in Gori improved through the integration of multi-source data, with reductions in both omission and commission errors compared to approaches relying solely on Sentinel-2. Small parcels, which are typically underrepresented in automated workflows, were more reliably detected due to the spatial refinement provided by PlanetScope imagery. In Dedoplistskaro Municipality, where agricultural fields are larger and more homogeneous (Figure 4), the delineation results exhibited higher overall accuracy and consistency. If in the case of Gori it was about 60%, in the case of Dedoplistskaro it was up to 70%. The regular geometry of parcels and the dominance of annual crops facilitated clearer boundary detection, even when using Sentinel-2 imagery independently. Nevertheless, the addition of PlanetScope further enhanced boundary sharpness and reduced positional uncertainty.

Figure 3. Aerial images of two study areas: 1-in Gori Municipality, 2-in Dedoplistskaro Municipality.

Figure 4. Results of parcel delineation: 1-in Gori Municipality, 2-in Dedoplistskaro Municipality.

The addition of PlanetScope imagery to the process facilitated the detailed representation of small-scale objects.

The temporal dimension played a crucial role in this region, as crop phenology captured through NDVI time series enabled the identification of actively cultivated fields and differentiation from fallow or abandoned land. Seasonal patterns observed in the April–July period were sufficient to characterize crop cycles.

Compared to Gori, fewer segmentation errors were observed in Dedoplistskaro, particularly in terms of boundary fragmentation and over-segmentation. The method showed strong agreement with reference cadastral data, indicating that large-scale agricultural systems are more amenable to automated delineation workflows.

A comparative analysis between the two municipalities highlights the influence of landscape structure on delineation performance. Fragmented and heterogeneous environments, such as Gori, require a stronger reliance on high-resolution imagery and advanced feature extraction techniques, including texture and edge detection. In contrast, homogeneous agricultural systems, such as Dedoplistskaro, benefit more directly from temporal

analysis and can achieve satisfactory results with moderate spatial resolution data.

A comparison between the two regions highlights the influence of landscape structure on delineation performance. Fragmented and heterogeneous environments require a stronger reliance on high-resolution data and more advanced feature extraction techniques. In contrast, more homogeneous agricultural systems benefit more directly from temporal analysis and can achieve good results with moderate spatial resolution. Overall, the integration of multi-source data consistently improved both boundary detection and the identification of land-use status. The method proved capable not only of mapping parcel geometry but also of providing insights into whether parcels are actively used or potentially abandoned.

4 Discussion

The findings of this study confirm that combining multiple satellite data sources can significantly improve parcel delineation, especially in complex agricultural landscapes. In Gori, the fragmented nature of agricultural land and the presence of orchards created clear limitations for

automated delineation. Nevertheless, the use of multi-temporal NDVI helped to partially overcome these issues by capturing differences in vegetation dynamics that are not visible in single-date imagery. In Dedoplistskaro, the more uniform structure of agricultural fields allowed for higher accuracy, demonstrating how landscape characteristics influence the performance of delineation methods. At the same time, the results show that even in relatively simple environments, the addition of high-resolution imagery can further improve boundary precision. Despite these positive results, some limitations remain. In our case, this concerned parcels occupied by perennial crops, which were bordered by windbreaks (Gori Municipality). In this case, the boundary between the two objects was low-contrast and the actual parcel shape varied.

The approach still depends on the availability of suitable satellite data, and performance decreases in areas with dense vegetation or complex canopy structures. Future work could explore the use of deep learning methods and longer multi-season datasets to improve robustness and adaptability.

5 Conclusions

This study demonstrates that the integration of multi-source satellite imagery provides an effective solution for automated agricultural parcel delineation in data-limited environments such as Georgia. By combining the temporal strengths of Sentinel-2 with the spatial detail of PlanetScope imagery, the proposed approach improves both boundary detection and the identification of cultivated and potentially abandoned land. The method performs well across different types of agricultural landscapes, although results vary depending on parcel structure and fragmentation. Overall, the workflow offers a practical and scalable framework for land administration, agricultural monitoring, and policy support. Future research should focus on incorporating advanced machine learning techniques and expanding temporal coverage to further enhance accuracy and support continuous monitoring of agricultural systems.

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